

ENTREPRENEURIAL CHARACTERISTICS AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMEs) IN PLATEAU STATE.

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ABSTRACT

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) have proven to be vital for economic growth. Furthermore, the sustainability of SMEs is important especially for developing countries. Entrepreneurial traits are the driving force for SMEs sustainability thus needs to be investigated. The objective of this study is to explore the relationship between entrepreneurial characteristics (locus of control, risk-taking attitude, innovative and need for achievement) and financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State. The study adopts the theoretical lens of personality based theory. Using a descriptive research design, primary data was collected via questionnaires. 287 questionnaires were distributed to management and supporting personnel working at top and middle management level of various SMEs in Plateau State. Regression analysis via SPSS was used to analyze the data. The study found that entrepreneurial characteristics contribute to the financial performance of SMEs in Plateau state. This study concludes that locus of control relates with financial performance through its ability to determine one's own destiny, willingness to accept both positive and negative consequences of one's decisions and actions, risk taking through understanding of business opportunities and willingness to take calculated risk for a sure rate of return, thus facilitating positive financial performance of SMEs. Our study argues that the character of an entrepreneur is relevant thus enables a firm achieve the desired financial outcome. Also, this study contributes to growing body of literature on entrepreneurial characteristics and financial performance of SMEs.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Characteristics, Financial Performance, SMES

Introduction

Across the globe, it has been established that the activities of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are critical for the economic growth and development of a country. Singh, Pathak, Shee, Kazmi and Parker (2013) stressed that SMEs are the greatest profit opportunity in European markets. In Nigeria, SMEs accounted for about 80% of the industrial sector in terms of number and employees (Oyeniyi & Adeniji, 2010). Regardless of this, there is also high number of failed and collapsed SMEs in Nigeria due to low sales and profitability, poor business decision, high cost of production, competition with foreign products and low market share (Idowua, Olusola, and Olawale, 2016). It is not yet determined if the low profitability and sales are as result of entrepreneurs' incapability or inability to take calculated risk, to react sharply to the moves of the competition or to create new and acceptable ideas. In a bid

to address the SMEs' situation, successive administrations in Nigeria have made concerted efforts to assist SMEs move from dwindling production levels as well as their failure rates. These efforts include the establishment of Bank of Industries, Microfinance Banks and National Directorate for Employment (NDE), the establishment of Peoples Banks, Agricultural Development Bank (ADB), Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN), National Economic Empowerment Development Strategy (NEEDS) SURE-P and even the introduction of National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP). In spite of the enormous effort put in by the government through various programmes and policies to revive and establish a relevant foundation for SME's in Nigeria, there has been no substantial improvement realized from them in terms of financial performance.

Previous studies have demonstrated that there are links between entrepreneurial characteristics and performance of SMEs (Al-Damen, 2015; Tambwe, 2015; Adeoye, 2013; Osemeke, 2012) but there are very few studies that have been conducted to examine how the character of entrepreneurs' affect the financial performance in terms of sales growth and profitability of the SMEs in Plateau State. Phelan (2014) observed that the most important factor that influence the financial performance of SMEs in terms of sales growth and profitability, is the entrepreneurial characteristics of an entrepreneur which is the function of locus of control, risk taking attitude, innovativeness, and need for achievement. SMEs owners/managers are expected to possess certain entrepreneurial characteristics in order to be competitive and contribute to the success of a firm. Entrepreneurial characteristic is something that entrepreneurs or owners of SMEs need to build, instill, foster and maintain. Therefore, in order to engender the financial performance of small and medium enterprises, top management leaders ought to take into consideration, the probable effects of entrepreneurial characteristics as a function of locus of control, risk taking attitude, innovativeness, and need for achievement. Over the year's entrepreneurial characteristics and financial performance of SMEs have received less attention in diverse contexts across the world (Henning & McKelvey, 2020; Lin, Lu, Liu & Zhang, 2016). Hence, this study attempts to fill the gap.

SMEs across the globe are the backbone for employment generation and poverty alleviation. The birth, growth, and sustainability of SMEs are critical to the attainment of economic growth and development of countries, and most of the SMEs do not celebrate their fifth years in Nigeria (Bakar & Zainol, 2015). This calls for further investigation into factors that predict superior financial performance of SMEs in Nigeria. Therefore, this study sort to find solutions to the problems associated with the superior financial performance that lead to the growth and survival of small and medium enterprises through the influence of entrepreneur character as a function of locus of control, risk taking attitude, innovativeness, and need for achievement. Evidence suggests that low sales and profitability, poor business decisions are amongst the primary factors contributing to the failure of SMEs (Idowua et al., 2016). This research was conducted to explore the relationships between trait entrepreneurial characteristics and financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State. This study aspires to indicate the type of entrepreneurial characteristics an entrepreneur will need to have, cultivate and/ or develop, in order to drive his or her venture forward successfully. To the scholars, the findings of this study will add value to the existing body of knowledge as it recommends ways for improvement of financial performance by leveraging on entrepreneurs' character also the findings of this study will help SMEs in all sectors in evaluating the importance of entrepreneurs' character on their financial performance in terms of bolstering sales and profitability and it will also be helpful to the policy makers because it will shed more light on entrepreneurial characteristics and financial performance which will assist in formulating entrepreneurship strategies. This study will help to identify the gaps in entrepreneur character

as a performance strategy in SMEs. The study investigates the relationship between entrepreneurial characteristics as a function of locus of control, risk taking attitude, innovativeness, need for achievement and financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State.

Literature Review

Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship has led to the development and expansion of new industries as well as the existing industries. Entrepreneurship is being controlled and directed by entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs take bold steps and giant stride to achieve his goals and objectives for the enterprises. Entrepreneurs take risk by creating or transforming thoughts into new ventures and to make the new ventures penetrate the market. Thus, an entrepreneur is the individual that identifies opportunities, gather necessary resources, creates and is ultimately responsible for the performance of the firm (Adegbite, Ilori, Irefin, Abereijo & Aderemi, 2007; Oyeniyi & Adeniji, 2010). According to Misra & Kumar (2000), the terms that link the definitions of an entrepreneur are innovation, opportunity recognition, profit, promoting economic growth, venture creation and change. Al-Damen (2015) defined entrepreneur as the person who creates something new and innovative in an existing economy. Thus, this study defines an entrepreneur as the person who conceives an idea, takes the risk of transforming the idea into business ventures by making the idea known and selling the ideas in the target market for the purpose of financial and non-financial rewards. Although the concept of an entrepreneur is defined in a number of different ways, the basis of the definitions is that entrepreneurs are individuals who make different decisions, based on advancing himself/herself and the business. Personal characteristics and decision-making skills have been linked to the management capacity of SMEs, thereby indicating the importance of entrepreneurial characteristics in SMEs (Nuthall, 2001). According to scholars, traits approach has been linked to the study of entrepreneurship in an attempt to understand the entrepreneur and entrepreneurship (Kobia & Sikalieh, 2010; Phelan, 2014). The traits approach is based on the psychology of an entrepreneur and draws from theories based on personality, focusing on the individual as a promoter of entrepreneurship (Phelan, 2014). The basis of the approach is that entrepreneurial individuals have different personality traits from the rest of the world's population. Accordingly, a person with entrepreneurial skills can be distinguished from others through the identification of specific personality traits such as locus of control, risk-taking, innovativeness and need for achievement (Rotter, 1966; Kobia and Sikalieh, 2010; Phelan, 2014).

Locus of Control: originates from the work of Rotter (1966) who described it as the way a person expects that an outcome (due to their behaviour) can be influenced by their characteristics and how they react to a situation. Locus of control includes the expectations of an outcome due to fate or luck (Rotter, 1966). Therefore, internal locus of control is a person's belief of how they can exert control over their fortunes. External locus of control, on the other hand, is the belief that one does not have an influence on an outcome. People with an internal locus of control are more likely to display entrepreneurial behaviour, due to their need to determine (have control over) their own path (Mueller & Thomas, 2000). According to Schiebel (2002), the locus of control of a successful entrepreneur is his ability to control situations, as well as their outcomes. The literature accordingly suggests that individuals with a higher internal locus of control will be more entrepreneurial (Bonnet & Furnham, 1991; Mueller & Thomas, 2000).

Risk-Taking Attitude: according to Vesala et al. (2007), it is assumed that an entrepreneur takes calculated economic risks with the goal of maximizing profit. In SMEs, risk attitudes are usually categorized as risk-taking, risk-neutral and risk adverse. Entrepreneurship, however, creates an additional category of calculated risk-taking. For a manager to manage his risk does not necessarily mean avoiding risk, but rather managing the risk to one's own benefit. An entrepreneur may rationally take on a risk if there is a possibility for a reward. This, however, is something to be measured among entrepreneurs and is not necessarily an integral character trait (Phelan, 2014). The risk-taking attitude of an individual will determine the type of decisions they will make in regard to the SMEs business in general. Entrepreneurs are people who are considered to be optimistic, as well as having a certain level of self-confidence, which are traits of risk takers. An entrepreneur who is confident will be more likely to see an opportunity as less risky than someone who is less confident. A possible reason for the involvement of entrepreneurs in riskier events is that entrepreneurs evaluate opportunities in a more optimistic way than others do (Palich & Bagby, 1995).

Innovativeness: the seeking, creating, developing and implementing of new products or methods are seen as a description of innovativeness (Vesala, Peura & McElwee, 2007). An entrepreneur is involved with active, dynamic and competitive economic striving to seek out new opportunities (Stanworth & Curran, 1991; Stevenson & Jarillo, 2007). An entrepreneur is thus actively looking for new ways to do things, create things, or improve things. This constant search for "new ways" distinguishes entrepreneurs from other individuals, by them being innovative.

Need for Achievement: according to Hansemark (2003), the need for achievement is founded on the expectancy that one can do something better and faster than anyone else can, or better than before. Entrepreneurs have a need for achievement, and strive to make a difference in their own lives and those of others (Knudson, Wysocki, Champagne & Peterson, 2004). Need for achievement is an internal drive to succeed and achieve greater and better things (McClelland, 1965). He argued that the need for achievement is higher for entrepreneurs than it is for other individuals. However, Low and MacMillan (1988) found that the need for achievement that McClelland (1965) describes as being higher in entrepreneurs could also be high in a manager, a sales-person or other business related individuals.

Financial Performance

The objective for any business is to use inputs in order to create an output that can be sold for a profit, and the same can be said for SMEs. As SMEs considered a business, and the main objective, in the past, was to maximize profit (Carter & Rosa, 1998). Today, however, there are additional factors involved i.e. minimizing cost, increasing business growth, increasing family time, avoiding debt, and achieving sustainability to be successful; hence, the focus is more on the sustainability of the SMEs business for future generations (Olson, 2000). Financial performance is an important part of any business, be small or large. For SMEs to be successful, he or she needs to be able to determine the financial structure to assess whether the SMEs financial performance is viable. Effective record-keeping can help with determining the long-term performance, and provide an overall picture of the SMEs financial performance (Henning & McKelvey, 2020). Thus, the financial performance of SMEs is important in every sector, as it provides the measures needed to evaluate the financial

statements of the SMEs business to determine the success of the businesses performance. SMEs need financial statements to compare the actual performance of the business against the planned performance and past performance. Contentment with past performance may elevate future business aspirations, leading to an increase in the ambitions of the businesses' future SMEs. Therefore, constant evaluation and re-evaluation of the financial performance of the SMEs is considered important. Performance evaluation of any business is an important process where the owners receive feedback on the actions taken within the business to stay competitive and increase profitability (Burja & Burja, 2013). Entrepreneurs that want to be successful in a volatile economic environment need to manage their resources better and be more effective business managers. According to Reynolds, Bygrave, Autio & Arenius (2004), financial perspective is linked to profits, wealth creation, economic growth and sales growth, while non-financial perspective is associated with competitive advantage and increased productivity. This study focuses on the financial performance of SMEs.

Employee Characteristics and Financial Performance

The relationship between entrepreneurial characteristics and financial performance is vital. Extant studies suggest that entrepreneurial traits drives firm performance negatively or positively, and vice versa (Henning & McKelvey, 2020). However, the influence of entrepreneurial characteristics on firm performance is underexplored (Gerli, Gubitta & Tognazzo, 2011). Scholars have suggested frameworks for determining the relationship between entrepreneurial characteristics and firm performance (Man, 2001; Man, Lau & Chan, 2002; Ahmad, Ramayah, Wilson & Kummerow, 2010). Some suggest that the focus should be on the individual entrepreneur, while others suggest that the focus should not be on the individual, but rather on the whole firm. In this study, the focus however is on the individual entrepreneur in order to determine business success. Man et al. (2002) suggested that four entrepreneurial characteristics established from the trait approach could be compared with two factors linked to financial performance. The two factors include sales growth and profitability. According to Ahmad et al. (2010) and Phelan (2014), for a firm to be successful, specific entrepreneurial characteristics (locus of control, risk taking attitude, innovativeness, and personal competencies) are needed. It is therefore important that entrepreneurs inculcate the relevant competencies to increase their firm's financial and non-financial performance.

Methodology

The design that was adopted for this study is a descriptive and hypotheses testing survey design; this was employed to empirically investigate the relationships among variables of the research. For this study, quantitative approach was used in analyzing the data collected.

The population that was used in this study includes the management personnel as well as supporting personnel of the SMEs working at the top and middle management level within the firm of various SMEs in Plateau State, involved in activities across various industries from manufacturing, construction, agricultural and other sectors. The total estimated figure for the population arrived at, based on SMEDAN (2013), Plateau state has two thousand one hundred and eighty (2180) SMEs.

In order to determine the sample size for the study, Yamane (1967) formula for calculating sample size for finite population was adopted: $n = N / 1 + N (e)^2$, where: n = sample size, N = finite population size which is 2180, e = maximum acceptable error margin which is 5%. By calculation, $n = 2,180 / 1 + 2180 (0.05)^2$, $n = 337.98 \sim 338$. Therefore, the sample size derived for this study is Three Hundred and Thirty-Eight (338) SMEs.

However, the Three Hundred and Thirty-Eight SMEs were selected using random sampling technique so as to increase the sampling precision for the study.

For the purpose of this study, primary data was employed. The data was collected with the aid of a questionnaire properly drafted using the 5 point Likert-scale. The questionnaire instrument employed for this study was adapted (Henning & McKelvey, 2020, Neneh, 2011; McClelland, 1965; Stevenson & Jarillo, 2007; Phelan, 2014; Schiebel, 2002; Mueller & Thomas, 2000; Man et al., 2002; Ahmad et al., 2010). The validity of measurement was established through content validity which was given to other researchers to ascertain whether the questionnaire item adequately cover the domain of the construct it was also certified by researcher's supervisor and experts in entrepreneurship to ensure validity of questionnaire items. The reliability was calculated by using the statistical methods such as the Cronbach Alpha.

Table 1: Pre-test Reliability Analysis

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Locus of Control	0.725
Risk Taking Attitude	0.816
Innovation	0.832
Need for Achievement	0.910
Financial Performance	0.872
Overall Average Alpha for the instrument (α)	0.826

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The result of the pre-test showed that the scales were considered as reliable (Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.80$) and the manipulation checks were valid. The aim of the reliability as a quality criterion is to minimize errors and give stable results of data collection.

Regression analysis was used to analyze the relationships between the variables. As such, the relationships between entrepreneurial characteristics (locus of control, risk taking attitude, innovation, and need for achievement) and SME financial performance. The underlying assumptions of the linear regression, which are linearity, normality and homoscedasticity were tested.

The model is $FP = \beta_0 + \beta_1LC + \beta_2RT + \beta_3IN + \beta_4NA + \Sigma_1$,

Where FP = Financial Performance,

β_0 = Intercept,

β_1 = Regression Coefficient,

LC = Locus of Control,

RT = Risk-Taking,

IN = Innovativeness,

NA = Need for Achievement,

Σ_1 = Error.

Data Analysis

The method of data analysis employed for this study was linear regressions to examine the relationship between locus of control, risk taking, innovativeness, need for achievement and financial performance of SMEs.

Table 1: Questionnaire Response Rate

	Number
Copies of Questionnaires	338
Copies of questionnaires returned	308
Copies of questionnaires not returned	30
Number of questionnaires deemed usable	287
Percentage of questionnaire used	84.0%
Percentage of questionnaires not used	16.0%
Total percentage	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The questionnaire response rate shows that about 84% (287) of the respondents correctly filled the questionnaire thus usable, while 16% (i.e. 30) were unusable. The response rate is deemed high.

Table 2: Respondents Profile

Attribute		Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Female	142	49.5
	Male	145	50.5
	Total	287	100.0
Age Distribution	25 years	35	12.2
	26 - 30 years	54	18.8
	31 - 35 years	53	18.5
	36 - 40 years	56	19.5
	41 - 45 years	65	22.6
	46 - 50 years	24	8.4
	Total	287	100.0
Educational Qualification	OND/NCE	48	16.7
	Degree/HND	96	33.4
	Master degree	104	36.2
	PhD	39	13.6
	Total	287	100.0
Job Rank	Top Management	71	24.7

	Middle Management	143	49.8
	Lower Management	73	25.4
	Total	287	100.0
Length of Service	Below 5 years	74	25.8
	6 - 10 years	146	50.9
	11 - 15 years	67	23.3
	Total	287	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Demographic and personal data of the respondents as shown by gender revealed that 145 (50.5%) of respondents were male, while 142 (49.5%) were female. This shows that male respondents participated more in the study than female respondents. Demographic data for age also shows that 35 (12.2%) of the respondents were below ages of 26 years, 54 (18.8%) were in the age group of 26-30 years, 53 (18.5%) were between the ages of 31-35 years, 56 (19.5%) were between the ages of 36-40 years, 65 (22.6%) were between the ages of 41-45 years, while 24 (8.4%) were between 46-50 years of age. For educational qualification of respondents 48 (16.7%) of respondents possessed the Ordinary National Diploma (OND/NCE), 96 (33.4%) had the Bachelor’s degree and Higher National Diploma, 104 (36.2%) were Master degree holders, 39 (13.6%) were PhD holders. The data also revealed that 71 (24.7%) of the respondent surveyed were Top Management staff members, 73 (25.4%) lower management staff while 143 (49.8%) surveyed were Middle Management. Demographic data of respondents by length of service also shows that 74 (25.8%) of the respondents were below 5 years, 146 (50.9%) were between the group of 6-10 years, while 67 (23.3%) were between the group of 11-15 years of length of service.

Table 3: Regression Coefficients of Locus of Control

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	4.560	.736		6.192	.000
1. Locus of Control	.787	.035	.802	22.634	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Table 3 shows that entrepreneurial characteristics - locus of control has a significant relationship with financial performance, with a t-value of -22.63 and p value of .000.

Table 4: Regression Coefficients of Risk Taking

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	10.491	.597		17.560	.000
Risk Taking	.501	.028	.726	17.845	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Table 4 shows that there is a statistically determinant relationship between risk taking attitude and financial performance with t-value of 17.85 and a p value of .000.

Table 5: Regression Coefficients of Innovativeness

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	14.050	1.367		10.277	.000
Innovativeness	.341	.064	.302	5.347	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

The result in Table 5 shows that there is a statistically determinant relationship between innovativeness and financial performance of selected SMEs in Plateau State as it is associated with sig-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.005 or 5%. With a t-value of 5.35 and a p- value of .000 we can conclude that there is a significant relationship between innovativeness and financial performance.

Table 6: Regression Coefficients of Need for Achievement

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	14.050	1.367		10.277	.000
Need for Achievement	.348	.064	.302	7.347	.030

a. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

The result in Table 6 shows that there is a statistically determinant relationship between need for achievement and financial performance of selected SMEs in Plateau State as it is associated with sig-value of 0.030 which is less than 0.005 or 5%. We can therefore conclude that there is a significant relationship between need for achievement and financial performance with a t and p value of 7.35 and .030 respectively.

Table 7: Path Relationship

Hypotheses	Test	Result	Remark
H0₁: There is no significant relationship between locus of control and financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State.	Regression .000	Significant	Rejected
H0₂: There is no significant relationship between risk taking and financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State.	Regression .000	Significant	Rejected

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between innovativeness and financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State.	Regression .004	Significant	Rejected
H0₄: There is no significant relationship between need for achievement and financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State.	Regression .030	Significant	Rejected

Source: SPSS Version 23

Table 7 indicates that all hypothesis (locus of control, risk taking, innovativeness, need for achievement) were significant (.000, .000, .004, .030 respectively) thus rejected. This shows that all variables of entrepreneurial characteristics (locus of control, risk taking, innovativeness, need for achievement) contribute to financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the analysis in this study shows that locus of control significantly affects financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State. Our result also validates the findings of Oyedijo (2012) who found that locus of control leads to increasing performance among SMEs better than those without locus of control. This study tried to ascertain the relationship between risk taking attitude and financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State. The findings reveal that there is a significant relationship between risk taking attitude and financial performance of SMEs and is consistent with other researchers (Jeje, 2020; Miller & LeBruton-Miller, 2011; Egele, Muhammad & Mutenyo, 2014). Furthermore, the result of the analysis showed that innovativeness significantly predicts financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State. This is consistent with previous findings (Bigliardi, 2013; Olaolu & Obaji, 2020). Finally, our results show that need for achievement significantly predicts financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State. This is consistent with previous findings (Handrito, Slabbinck & Vanderstraeten, 2020; Sengupta & Debnath, 1994). Low and MacMillan (1988) found that firms that have better performance would also have a higher level of need for achievement.

Conclusions

The study examined entrepreneurial characteristics and financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State. Entrepreneurial characteristics in this study are the means by which an organization establishes and re-establishes its fundamental set of relationships with its environment. Variable used to measure entrepreneurial characteristics were locus of control, risk taking, innovativeness, and need for achievement. The study established a positive relationship between the dimensions of entrepreneurial characteristics and financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State. The result also showed that the four independent variables established a positive relationship with SMEs financial performance.

This study adds more to the knowledge and understanding on entrepreneurial characteristics and financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State. Drawing from the personality based theory, this study argues that the character of an entrepreneur is very relevant and could enable a firm achieve the desired financial outcome. The theory considers certain individual traits to be the most strategically significant resources of the firm that does

not depreciate with other productive factors and can generate increasing economic return to the firm.

The study is in line with the small but growing body of literature on entrepreneurial characteristics and financial performance of SMEs and shows that locus of control relates with financial performance through its ability to determine one's own destiny, willing to accept both positive and negative consequences of one's decisions and actions, risk taking through understanding of business opportunities, and willingness to take a calculative risk for a sure rate of return, these would facilitate financial performance of SMEs. The study also examined the relationship between innovativeness and financial performance and it was established that a relationship exists between both variables and finally the study established a strong correlation between need for achievement and financial performance of SMEs. Overall, the study indicated that entrepreneurial characteristics contribute to the financial performance of SMEs in Plateau State. Entrepreneurs with innovativeness and motivation should possess capabilities such as business acumen, commercial orientation, leadership oriented capabilities and carry out business practices such as teamwork, marketing practices and performance management practices and strategic planning practices also entrepreneurs should ensure that their need for achievement is an internal drive to succeed and achieve greater and better things, strive to make a difference in their own lives and those of others.

The scope of this study is a limitation. Few SMEs were selected within the SME sector thus the findings of the study cannot be generalized in a larger context across cultures of other countries, sectors and business environment. As a result of these, the result from the relationships between entrepreneurial characteristics and financial performance of SMEs in other studies may differ. Also, the survey research is limited in its capacity due to access to funding and time.

Future studies should adopt the use of reliable secondary data which are non-perceptual in nature, that could reflect SMEs activities and performance over time, rather than subjective, self-reported perceptual measures. Future research should examine the variables in other research context, sectors, countries and business environment so as to increase the generalizability of the findings. Lastly, further studies could examine the different approaches to entrepreneurial characteristics and linking it with SMEs non-financial performance.

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